

CORRES NUTRITION IN INTESTINAL DISEASES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract

The article highlights the main cereals that affect the bowel. It is cereals such as barley, oats, corn, wheat, rye, millet, and millet and are widely used for rehabilitation of the intestine.

Keywords: nutrition, diet, disease, intestinal.

Actuality of theme. As you know, one of the components of health is proper and rational nutrition. Cereal products, especially whole grain, and proper heat treatment, are occupied by the largest amount of food. As you know, nutritional value depends on the method of cooking. Useful properties are stored in products where the cooking method is with prolonged heat treatment or steamed. However, the vitamin value of products is stored with its minimal processing[2].

Cereals include the following plants (products):

- “Barley,
- “Oats,
- Corn,
- wheat,
- rye,
- millet,
- etc.

The goal of the work. To evaluate the properties of cereals in diseases of the intestine.

Research results. It is believed that cereal grain is an energy -value product.

The cereal grain contains:

- up to 88% of dry matter,
- up to 14% protein,
- up to 3 % fat (and oat grain and corn 6 %),
- up to 70% of nozotichexitive substances presented mainly by starch,
- up to 4 % of ash.

There are two types of fiber:

- Golosern (2 - 3 %),
- film (5 - 9 %). These include barley, millet and oats).

It is known that 1 kg of grain of cereals contains 1 - 1.3 k. nutrition, and with a content of 67 - 106 g of digestible protein. Proteins have low amounts of lysine, methionine, tryptophan and essential amino acids [4].

The grain also contains fat that is saturated with unsaturated fatty acids, namely oleic and linoleic acid.

The grain also contains minerals, namely the amount of phosphorus greater than calcium and vitamins of group B, C and E.

Comparing the grain plants found that the highest nutrition contains corn grain, where there are many:

- carbohydrates,
- starch (about 70 - 80%),
- fats (about 6-10 %).

However, it is the smallest protein that is contained in corn and the highest digestibility of organic matter.[6]

The second in its structure is barley - the nutrition of which is from 1 kg 1.2 k. digestible protein.

The third in its structure is oats that have an excitatory effect. Oats have 1 kg of oats 1 k. nutritional value, including fat up to 5 % and fiber up to 10 %. In fat, essential fatty acids and hormone -like substances are found, which causes its dietary properties.

Wheat includes up to 15 % protein and wheat gluten and its nutrition is 1.28k.

Priority tasks in the treatment of inflammatory diseases of the intestine are to control the course of the disease, to achieve remission, to prevent complications and to improve the quality of life of patients for a favorable vital and social prognosis.

After treatment of inflammatory diseases of the intestine during the period of nutrition should be varied:

- increase in the use of whole cereals;
- consumption of five vegetables and fruits per day;
- restriction of sugar consumption (up to 25 g per day) and salt (up to 5 g per day), fat and fatty dishes;
- apply careful methods of culinary processing;
- daily consume low-fat dairy products, regularly eat moderate amounts of meat, fish, eggs- 2-3 times a week.[3]

It is found that the fiber is cleaved in the colon, which secretes into the blood all sorts of nutrients that can have anti -inflammatory effect. Everything that happens in our colon has a protective effect of whole grain products against type 2 diabetes [5].

Studies show that who consumes the portions of whole grain has a lower body mass index, which reduces the tendency to gain weight [1].

Conclusion. Given the above, it can be said that cereals are an urgent component not only for intestinal diseases, but also in its normal work.

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